

METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING CADETS OF HIGHER MILITARY EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS TO CREATIVE THINKING THROUGH THE USE OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation: *this article explores how to use interactive techniques and the role of modern techniques in the study of military terms and their application in the course of a lesson using examples.*

Keywords: *interactive methods, graphic organizers, interactive strategies, military terms.*

Аннотация: *в этой статье на примерах рассматривается, как использовать интерактивные методы и роль современных методик в изучении военных терминов и их применении в ходе урока.*

Ключевые слова: *интерактивные методы, графические органайзеры, интерактивные стратегии, военные термины.*

Annotatsiya: *ushbu maqolada interfaol metodlardan qanday foydalanish va harbiy atamalarni o'rganishda zamonaviy metodlarning o'rni va ularni dars jarayonida misollar yordamida qo'llash o'rganiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *interaktiv usullar, grafik organayzerlar, interaktiv strategiyalar, harbiy atamalar.*

INTRODUCTION

We fully believe that English teachers in higher military educational institutions should have cultural knowledge with foreign language qualifications. Foreign languages and cultural consciousness can be considered a “critical ability”. But not enough class hours are allocated for English, or the language proficiency of Cadets is very low when it is, the process of learning a foreign language is difficult. Training in English is a complex process that involves time, human and financial resources. To each army can speak and write foreign languages, verbally military personnel who can understand speech or written text, literal and figurative forms of language are needed. The inability to speak the main language of NATO can be considered a real obstacle for any military who participates in international tasks.

LITERATURE ANALYZE

Language Teaching is such a complex process that it is difficult to say that I have reached the end. Today, the teaching of foreign languages is considered one of the most pressing issues. Because as we all know, the latest science news, the fact that achievements, ideas, discoveries are now published in English, one of the most important languages of the world, the language of Science and technology, among many countries, has given impetus to the strengthening of the emphasis on foreign languages in our country.

Since the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, deep socio-political and economic changes have been taking place in our homeland. The increase in the prestige of our state on a global scale and the integration of our republic into the world community has essentially renewed the relationship between language and society. Nowadays, great importance is attached to the study and teaching of foreign languages in our country.

From this situation, the socio-political, scientific and technical and cultural situation in the republic assumes a comparative-typological systematic study of Uzbek with other modern, secular foreign languages, which has the status of an official state language.

Today, a number of works are also carried out in institutions of higher military education with the aim of training and training mature officers with deep knowledge, modern thinking. One of the main goals is the ability of students in military educational institutions to read literature in foreign languages, internet information related to their profession, to form skills and qualifications to be able to communicate, to exchange ideas with foreign specialists

METHODOLOGY

At this point, we must emphasize that even at our University of Public Safety, English is for all stage cadets in practical classes improved programs have been created from unconventional interactive techniques that, according to these programs, encourage cadets to think creatively and independently effective implementation of the use and their application to the course process is carried out.

As an example, we can mention a number of interactive techniques. GTM (grammar translation method), TPR (teaching physical response), CLT (communicative language teaching), Direct method, ADEPT (analogy, diagram, example, plain English, technical definition) method, Silent way, Audio-lingual, TBL (task-based learning), CBL (content-based learning), PPP (presentation practice (product), Project method, Location method, etc. Within these, the project method is very effective and gives a good, self-expected result in the course of the lesson.

Because when we apply this method to the course process, the teacher directs cadets to Independent Education. At the same time supervises the learners, the subjects are taken from real military life, of course, the learner will have the opportunity to work in a group. This teaches cadets to think, to communicate. The adept method also helps to briefly cover a broader topic. The CBL method, on the other hand, is particularly suitable for the military field, where it is worked with a map.[1]

While the implementation of these techniques in the course process is a little complicated, the effect will be positive if we can clearly and correctly direct it to the lesson. The creation of a language environment in higher educational institutions of a non-philological orientation depends on the pedagogical skill of the teacher. Because working with terms is labor from the teacher and it takes time. Within the teaching methods, interactive methods are from methods suitable for the demand of modern pedagogy, which is divided into 3 groups.

- 1) graphic organizers
- 2) interactive strategies
- 3) interactive methods

Each of these is definitely used in a specific direction. While graphic organizers serve as a tool or educational method, strategies will require the teacher to take directions, and in an interactive method, someone will have to be evaluated. These are graphs from within t-scheme, BBB, think way, mental attack and analysis of concepts, which are included in organizers, are used a lot in the course of the lesson. In particular, the "analysis of concepts" method is of great help to cadets in the study of terms. For example, in the previous lesson a number of military terms mentioned are written and distributed on one side of the table, with cadets writing on the other side of the table to match the meaning of those words.

Picture 1. Effective teaching methods

The use of advanced and modern methods of teaching, new informative, so that cadets can master the studied applied Foreign Language Science- it is important to implement pedagogical technologies. The use of textbooks, educational and methodological manuals, handouts and electronic materials in mastering the subject is the activation of the course process, as well as the activity of cadets in the subject arouses relative interest.

Modern methods of education in the teaching of this discipline: the use of electron post, foreign TV channels, the internet, which combines virtual authenticity, that is, work with electronic educational literature and a database, the targeted use of the internet gives great effect in the formation and development of knowledge and skills. In the training of mature officer personnel, it is advisable to use interactive methods such as design, distance education, mental attack, group thinking, gallery, rotation, round table, Keys study, Jigsaw, use of small group competitions, internet news and advanced pedagogical technologies. [2]

CONCLUSION

Summing up from the above, it can be said that as a result of the large-scale work being done, the successes we are achieving in the field of education and in particular in the foreign language are the significant results of the "Uzbek model" in a short period is manifested as. The most impartial assessment is an outlier. One such recognition is also proud of the fact that our country occupies the leading positions in the world in terms of the level of development of the educational system. This is the current expression of the consistent reforms carried out by the leadership of our state, the high emphasis on education.

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